

TREATMENT OF PITTAJA PANDU THROUGH AYURVEDA: A CASE STUDY***Dr. Dhara V. Patel (MD Rachana Sharira)**

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How to cite this Article: *Dr. Dhara V. Patel (MD Rachana Sharira) (2026). Treatment Of Pittaja Pandu Through Ayurveda: A Case Study. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(4), 180–182. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 19/02/2026

Article Revised on 11/03/2026

Article Published on 01/04/2026

ABSTRACT

Pandu Roga described in *Ayurveda* closely resembles anemia described in modern medicine. It is characterized by pallor of skin, weakness, fatigue, and reduced vitality. Among the different types, *Pittaja Pandu* is mainly caused by the aggravation of *Pitta Dosha* leading to vitiation of *Rakta Dhatu* and impairment of normal metabolism. *Ayurveda* emphasizes correction of *Agni*, pacification of vitiated *Doshas*, and nourishment of *Dhatus* through herbal formulations and dietary regulation. The present case study evaluates the efficacy of *Ayurvedic* management in a patient suffering from *Pittaja Pandu*. The patient was treated with classical *Ayurvedic* formulations along with dietary and lifestyle modifications. Significant improvement was observed in clinical symptoms and hematological parameters after treatment. This case study highlights the potential role of *Ayurvedic* therapeutics in the management of *Pittaja Pandu*.

KEYWORDS: *Pandu Roga*, *Pittaja Pandu*, *Ayurveda*, Anemia, *Rakta Dhatu*, *Ayurvedic* management.**INTRODUCTION**

Pandu Roga is one of the important disorders described in *Ayurvedic* literature. According to *Charaka Samhita*, *Pandu* occurs due to vitiation of *Doshas*, particularly *Pitta*, which affects *Rasa* and *Rakta Dhatu* leading to pallor of the body.^[1] The disease is characterized by symptoms such as *Panduta* (paleness), *Daurbalya* (weakness), *Murchha* (giddiness), *Hridaya Spandana* (palpitation), and *Aruchi* (loss of appetite), *Rukshata* (roughness), *Shiteichha* (desire to coldness), *Truta* (thirstiness), *Sweda* (sweating), *Daurgandhyata* (foul smell), *Dah* (burning sensation), *Katu vaktrata* (bitter taste in mouth).^[2]

Among the five types of *Pandu* described in *Ayurveda*, *Pittaja Pandu* occurs due to excessive aggravation of *Pitta Dosha* caused by factors such as excessive intake of sour, salty, spicy foods, alcohol consumption, and exposure to heat.^[3] These factors lead to vitiation of *Rakta Dhatu* and impairment of normal hematopoiesis.

In modern medicine, *Pandu Roga* is often correlated with anemia, particularly iron deficiency anemia, where there is a reduction in hemoglobin concentration and red blood cells. *Ayurveda* provides a comprehensive approach to its management through *Shodhana* (purification therapy),

Shamana (pacifying therapy), herbal medications, and dietary modifications.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To evaluate the effect of *Ayurvedic* treatment in the management of *Pittaja Pandu* through a single case study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS**Study Design**

A single case study conducted in an *Ayurvedic* clinical setting.

Patient Information

A 29-years-old male patient presented with complaints of:

- Generalized weakness
- Fatigue
- Loss of appetite
- Paleness of skin and conjunctiva
- Mild dizziness

These symptoms had been present for approximately two months.

Clinical Findings

On examination the following findings were noted:

- Pallor of skin and conjunctiva
- Reduced appetite
- Mild tachycardia
- Weakness and lethargy

Laboratory Investigations

Parameter	Before Treatment
Hemoglobin	8.9 g/dL
RBC Count	3.4 million/mm ³
MCV	72 fL

These findings indicated anemia consistent with *Pandu Roga*.

Diagnosis

Based on clinical features and *Ayurvedic* examination (*Dashavidha Pariksha*), the condition was diagnosed as *Pittaja Pandu*.

Treatment Protocol

Internal Medicines

- 1) *Punarnava Mandura* – 500 mg twice daily after meals
- 2) *Draksharishta* – 20 ml twice daily with equal water

Clinical Improvement

Symptom	Before Treatment	After Treatment
Weakness	Severe	Mild
Fatigue	Severe	Mild
Loss of appetite	Present	Improved
Pallor	Marked	Reduced

3) *Amalaki Churna* – 3 gm twice daily with honey

Dietary Advice

- Intake of iron-rich foods such as green leafy vegetables and pomegranate
- Use of cow ghee and easily digestible diet
- Avoidance of spicy, sour, and oily foods

Lifestyle Advice

- Adequate rest
- Avoid excessive heat exposure
- Mild exercise and *Pranayama*

Duration of Treatment

30 days

RESULTS

After 30 days of treatment significant improvement was observed.

Hematological Improvement

Plot No 587, Near Sugar Factory, Borsara Road, Valsad-395007, Gujarat
Mob : +91 73629 77571 Email Id : health@valsad@gmail.com

Name : Date : 30-Dec-2025 12:43 pm
Age/Sex : 29 Yrs. / Male Receipt No : LAB2526/15379
UHID : 28518
Ref. By Dr. : SELF

PARAMETER	RESULT	NORMAL RANGE
Hemoglobin	8.9	13.5-18.0 g/dL %
WBC Count	7160	(4,000 - 10,000)/c. mm. in adults
RBC Count	3.4	4.5-6.5 m/c.mm.
DIFF WBC Count		
Band Form	00	% (0-5%)
Neutrophils	61	% (40-70%)
Lymphocytes	32	% (25-40%)
Eosinophils	05	% (1-4%)
Monocytes	02	% (0-10%)
Basophils	00	% (0-1%)
Hematocrit (PCV)	42.4	38-54 %
MCV	72	(86-100 fL)
MCH	27.9	(27-32 pg)
MCHC	35.1	(30-36 g/dL)
RDW	13.8	(11-14 %)
Platelet Count	315000	(150000 - 400000)/c. mm.
ESR	13	0-20 mm/hr.
Platelets in Smear	Adequate	
MPV	9	f (7.4-11.1)
PDW	16.1	f (8.6-15.2)

Method: Fully automated Mindray Hematology Analyser(S Part Differential)

Dr. Prashant Desai
MD Pathology Reg. G-15888

* Sample Received

Operator Name: Dr. Prashant Desai

Dr. Pragati M. Desai

MD Pathology Reg. G-33106

PrintDate & Time: 30-Dec-2025 02:30:00PM

Plot No 587, Near Sugar Factory, Borsara Road, Valsad-395007, Gujarat
Mob : +91 73629 77571 Email Id : health@valsad@gmail.com

Name : Date : 1-Feb-2026 9:30 am
Age/Sex : 29 Yrs. / Male Receipt No : LAB2526/18000
UHID : 32190
Ref. By Dr. : SELF

PARAMETER	RESULT	NORMAL RANGE
Hemoglobin	10.8	13.5-18.0 g/dL %
WBC Count	7160	(4,000 - 10,000)/c. mm. in adults
RBC Count	4.1	4.5-6.5 m/c.mm.
DIFF WBC Count		
Band Form	00	% (0-5%)
Neutrophils	61	% (40-70%)
Lymphocytes	32	% (25-40%)
Eosinophils	05	% (1-4%)
Monocytes	02	% (0-10%)
Basophils	00	% (0-1%)
Hematocrit (PCV)	41.2	38-54 %
MCV	80	(86-100 fL)
MCH	27.9	(27-32 pg)
MCHC	35.1	(30-36 g/dL)
RDW	13.8	(11-14 %)
Platelet Count	315000	(150000 - 400000)/c. mm.
ESR	14	0-20 mm/hr.
Platelets in Smear	Adequate	
MPV	9	f (7.4-11.1)
PDW	15.9	f (8.6-15.2)

Method: Fully automated Mindray Hematology Analyser(S Part Differential)

Dr. Prashant Desai
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* Sample Received

Operator Name: Dr. Prashant Desai

Dr. Pragati M. Desai

MD Pathology Reg. G-33106

PrintDate & Time: 2-Feb-2026 10:00 am

(Figure 1: Investigation report of CBC) (Before treatment)

(Figure 2: Investigation report of CBC) (After treatment)

Parameter	Before	After
Hemoglobin	8.9 g/dL	10.8 g/dL
RBC Count	3.4 million/mm ³	4.1 million/mm ³
MCV	72 fL	80 fL

The patient showed marked symptomatic and hematological improvement.

DISCUSSION

Pittaja Pandu occurs due to vitiation of *Pitta Dosha* leading to impairment of *Rakta Dhatu* formation. The therapeutic approach in *Ayurveda* focuses on correcting *Agni*, pacifying *Pitta Dosha*, and improving *Rakta Dhatu* production.

Punarnava Mandura is a classical *Ayurvedic* formulation widely used in *Pandu Roga*. It acts as a hematinic and improves hemoglobin levels by enhancing digestion and metabolism. *Draksharishta* acts as a digestive stimulant and improves appetite while supporting liver function. *Amalaki* possesses *Rasayana* and *Pitta*-pacifying properties and is rich in vitamin C, which enhances iron absorption.

Dietary regulation plays a significant role in the management of *Pandu*. Avoidance of *Pitta*-aggravating foods helps restore *Dosha* balance and improve metabolism.^[4]

The combined effect of these *Ayurvedic* interventions resulted in improvement in clinical symptoms and hematological parameters in the present case.

CONCLUSION

The present case study demonstrates that *Ayurvedic* management is effective in the treatment of *Pittaja Pandu*. Herbal formulations along with dietary and lifestyle modifications help correct *Dosha* imbalance, improve digestion, and enhance hemoglobin levels. *Ayurvedic* treatment can therefore be considered a safe and effective alternative approach for the management of *Pandu Roga*.^[5]

Further clinical studies with larger sample sizes are required to validate these findings.

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